

The Dialectic Epistemological Possibility of Objects related to Dark Energy and Dark Matter: Supplementary Study to the Epistemic Justification of Whole-Reason

Abstract

The study takes up the notion expounded in recent research that the modern disciplines of epistemology and science are implicitly engaged in a constant reciprocal dialectic, and then such a dialectic as has been historically characterized by the incognizant usage of an epistemically unjustified form of reasoning that connects, directs and delimits the respective discourses of these disciplines in conceptually problematic ways. Upon the newly formulated epistemology of reason the current discourse gives demonstration to how the identified dialectic can be explicitly utilized over the use of an epistemically justified form of reasoning to develop more sophisticated scientific knowledges of investigated objects. Here the cosmological phenomena related to the hypotheses of respectively dark energy and dark matter will be theoretically reflected through the logico-semantic structuring of the 'whole' form of reason, and thus rationally developed into a novel scientific formulation of potentially testable object knowledge.

Key words: Epistemology, Reason, Science, Dark Energy, Dark Matter.

1. Reasoned Reality Study

Dialectic epistemology, originally developed in Dreyer (2022), has been defined as the study of the nature and scope of *reasoned* human knowledge, and is thus openly performed as a reasoned knowledge theory. Through analyses of the reasoning used in the theorizations of preeminent scientists and philosophers it is rendered apparent, as a basic understanding of the new knowledge theory, that the respective disciplines of epistemology and science are implicitly engaged in a constant, reciprocal dialectic, such as hitherto has remained formally unrecognized and unchecked, and such as being characterized by the prejudiced (or pre-judgement) activity of a *form of reason*, called ‘elemental-reason’. From thence it follows, firstly, that the identified dialectic can be formally checked for its usage of either an epistemically justified, or an epistemically unjustified, reasoning form; and secondly, that a (provisionally) epistemically justified form of reason can be purposefully developed and then implemented in the dialectic identified between epistemology and science, hence making it possible for that dialectic to be rationally extended over the “discovery directive of testable object knowledge.” (Dreyer, 2022, p. 504) The latter possibility, simply stated, means that the formulation in epistemology of the concept – now following the logico-semantic structuring activity of an epistemically justified form of reason, named ‘whole-reason’ – can be dialectically translated into the theorization in science of the object, and so toward the rational development of scientific hypotheses and novel avenues of investigation.

Here a truncated *reasoned reality study* will provide an exemplar for such a discovery dialectic of science and epistemology that may in subsequent research be given fuller figure for experimental verification or falsification. Accordingly observe, in the epistemological framework of whole-reason, a failing dialectic of concept and object as relates to two unexpected empirical findings in cosmology and which in consequence have occasioned a growing sense of scientific crisis. The first finding of concern shook up the scientific community when two independent teams of astronomers announced in the late 1990s that the targeted Type Ia supernovae in high-redshift galaxies were systematically fainter than would be expected if the universe were expanding at either a constant or decelerating rate (Peebles & Ratra, 2003; Perlmutter et al., 1999; Riess et al., 1998); this bore the uncanny implication – uncanny for the then favoured *standard cold dark matter* model (SCDM) – that the universe had entered a period of accelerated expansion. The finding has been confirmed by a number of independent observations, including: temperature

anisotropies of the cosmic microwave background, inhomogeneities in the matter distribution, baryon acoustic oscillations, and weak lensing.¹ Consequently, in order to make the deceleration parameter (q) negative (q measures cosmic acceleration of universe expansion), and also make up for the density shortfall between the critical density and actual density estimated for the expanding universe, the concept of a repulsive form of gravity was *ad hoc* introduced – *dark energy*.² This is thought to be a mysterious ether-like fluid with negative pressure that doesn't dilute upon universe expansion and eventually in its repulsive action becomes capable over large distances of overcoming the gravitational attraction of the total mass-energy density in the universe. In Einstein's general relativity the dark energy is identified by the so-called *cosmological constant*, denoted by the Greek letter lambda (Λ); whereas in modern quantum field theory it is embodied by the non-zero energy density of the vacuum. Subsequent attempts to calculate the expected density of vacuum energy have yielded troubling results: the vacuum energy value is found to be many orders of magnitude larger than that indicated by the observed or actual value of the cosmological constant. This is referred to as the 'fine-tuning problem', and is generally considered the most fundamental problem in theoretical physics today. The problem has been influential in opening up a Pandora's Box of alternative formulations of dark energy in an ongoing effort to explain the exceedingly low energy density associated with its current proposition. Such include models of evolving dark energy like quintessence, phantom energy and quintom dark energy – each describing different and ordinarily conflicting object behaviours.

The second finding of concern originally peered its head in the 1930s when the astronomer Fritz Zwicky (1937) studied the radial velocity measurements (the velocity component along the line-of-sight) of several galaxies in the Coma cluster in order to determine their masses. Surprisingly he discovered that the orbital motions of the galaxies presented with flat *rotation curves*³ – which held the theoretical implication that the individual galaxies were moving too fast given the amount of visible matter in the cluster. He calculated that in order for the galaxies to exhibit such high rotational velocities and not quickly fly apart (by astronomical standards) the cluster would have to contain several hundred times more mass than that of stars in the visible galaxies. Hence he deduced that the Coma cluster must contain vast amounts of some hidden form of either

¹ For reference see Wang, Abdalla, Atrio-Barandela & Pavon (2016).

² For discussion see Nicolson (2007).

³ The graph produced by plotting the orbital velocity of an object against the distance from its assumed gravitational center.

exceedingly dim, or completely dark, matter – referring to the missing component as ‘dark matter’. Although Zwicky’s original calculations overreached the amount of gravitational (or *dynamical*) mass, subsequent research has found a definite excess of gravitational mass to luminous mass in all other galaxy groups and clusters, with the typical mass-to-light ratio for a cluster holding at around 300:1.⁴ Other cosmological observations showed that even individual galaxies, like our Milky Way, are dominated by dark matter (Rubin & Ford, 1970; Rubin, Ford Jr. & Thonnard, 1980); problematically however a more recent analysis, for example, of the kinematics of 412 stars in our solar neighbourhood has indicated the absence of dark matter (see Bidin, Carraro, Mendez & van Altena, 2010; Bidin, Carraro, Mendez & Smith, 2012; Bidin, Carraro, Mendez & Moyano, 2014), casting significant doubt on the prevailing understanding of the spatial distribution and nature of *galactic* dark matter and its supposed gravitational function in the role of missing matter. The current dilemma of galactic *versus* cosmological scale observations is exacerbated by the fact that the dark matter particle (i.e. the neutralino) proposed by the pertinent and preeminent physical theory, supersymmetry (SUSY), was not found by the Large Hadron Collider. This negative result is in agreement with the data from both the ACME and LUX experiments (for discussion see Hauser & Dröscher, 2017). Moreover, whereas the standard model of particle physics has been experimentally confirmed in all its aspects, the last 40 years of accelerator testing has provided no experimental evidence for the advanced physical theories developed to fill out the currently standard model of cosmology, the Λ CDM – wherein is reflected a critical-density geometrically flat universe filled with vacuum energy (Λ) and cold dark matter (CDM). The failing dialectic of concept and object in contemporary theoretical physics is well captured by Arun, Gudennavar and Sivaram (2017): “There are now numerous experiments in particle physics, astrophysics, and also in gravitational physics that have revealed not only massive contradictions between the so-called advanced theory and experimental data but also are forcing us to admit that there is a major rift between experimental data and our most fundamental understanding of physics. These completely unexplainable facts are pointing to a most severe crisis in physics.” (p. 515-516) The current crisis is deepened by the fact that a strong argument can be made from the perspective of both particle physics and astrophysics that the concept of dark matter, in particular, is fundamentally not falsifiable (see Sanders, 2010, p. 167-169), which in Popper’s (2002) view leaves in serious doubt the scientific status of dark matter models.

⁴ For discussion see Nicolson (2007).

Before the turn of the last century Sivaram (1994, 1999) made the simple point that if future particle experiments still do not yield any evidence for the existence of dark matter – as have become the experiments of our past and present – alternative theoretical explanations will have to be considered.⁵ In the epistemological dialectic of whole-reason such explanations must in their epistemic dimension be developed through the *logic emmanal* structuring⁶ of the concerned concepts of the proposed cosmological model. Here in particular a cosmological dynamic is put forward for the purpose (or the rational design) of scientific investigation and the possible achievement of ‘perstemic’ explanation⁷; a cosmological dynamic, moreover, that will be rationally developed and integrated by dialectically drawing on certain concepts which over scientific time have become methodologically selected as critical components of our explicatively and predictively most successful object theories, like Newtonian mechanics and Einsteinian general relativity. In the reasoned reality study the next *sine qua non* conceptualities of scientific thought are utilized: the concepts of time, space, form (or object) and motion. The ontological aspect of the afore-specified concepts is framed in logical agreement with whole-reason, and so logically structured in the conceptual character of the absolute and the relative, as follows. In the difference dimension of the logic emmanon nature of things, all universe objects are in motion as the difference of objects, thus objects move separately as parts of the non-local whole. This is described as the *relative motion* of an object: whereby an object is understood as a local identity of form that carries a relativistic character in its spatial and temporal relations to other such form identities. In the sameness dimension of the logic emmanon nature of things, all universe objects are in motion as the sameness of objects, thus objects move together as the non-local whole (of the actualizing present). This is described as the *absolute motion* of an object (and of all objects):

⁵ More recent discussions regarding current and future searches for dark matter and dark energy at colliders and other detection experiments, include Arbey & Mahmoudi (2021), Chadha-Day, Ellis & Marsh (2022), and Vagnozzi, Visinelli, Brax, Davis & Sakstein (2021).

⁶ The *logic emmanon*, with its descriptive derivations, represents the epistemologically formalized logic component of whole-reason that is theoretically developed to function as a conscious/subconscious primer which, through its distinct logico-semantic structure, directs the ordering activity of reason; and hence logically establishes the reasoning *form* of whole-reason. See Dreyer (2022).

⁷ The *perstemic*, and such a type of explanation, represents an epistemological concept in the theory of whole-reason which provides justification for why reason is required not only to be able to account for observed reality, but also justifies how reason, through the functionality of the concept in relation to the object, is capable in principle of producing true knowledge (i.e. perfectly logical reflection) *versus* mere opinion (i.e. imperfectly logical reflection). Moreover, for the perstemic determination of concept knowledge and/or object knowledge there is necessitated to occur a whole-reasoned resolution through a dialectic of epistemic justification and scientific explanation. See Dreyer (2022).

whereby an object is understood as a local identity of form that carries an absolutistic character in spatial and temporal relation to other such form identities through the non-local identity of form shared by all objects.

The simultaneously relativistic and absolutistic character of whole-reasoned object motion can be formulated in the spatio-temporal-forma terms of Erwin Schrödinger's infamous thought experiment – where the change over time in the condition of a cat (living or dead) in a deadly quantum chamber is described by the development of the wavefunction. In the logic of whole-reason the cat will not only go through different local identities as the condition of its form may change over time, i.e. the condition of being alive or dead; but will at once exist also as the same non-local identity through time, i.e. the condition of being both alive and dead. By the logical structuring of whole-reason, neither of the possible conditions of the cat being alive or dead is understood as an identity in itself, but rather as identities *through the whole* – which thus includes the shared identity of a *dead and alive cat* in the sameness of the non-local whole. Accordingly, whether the cat in the chamber be alive or dead and in relative motion in the form of either condition, it will ever at the time of its form be in absolute motion as the pervading spatio-temporal-forma reality of the sameness of all possible conditions. The whole form of reason and Schrödinger's wavefunction are therefore set in descriptive agreement about the existing conditions of the quantum entangled cat.

For the thinking of the cosmological dynamic here proposed, considerations about the relationship of the relative and absolute dimensions of reality in its actualizing totality of motion – i.e. the actual motion of objects in difference and in sameness; denoted *whole-reality motion* or *whole-universe motion* – such as can be rationally qualified in terms of the logic emmanal structuring of the space and time relations of forms, are of determinative import. First consider that in whole-reason no form exists as a thing-in-itself, and so no form *per se* physically exists in relative motion to absolute motion. Every form exists as a *thing-through-the-whole*, and so every form physically exists unto absolute motion only through its relative motion to other forms. As such, no local form by itself possesses magnitude or direction in relation to absolute motion (which by definition is also its own motion) – it is neither a vector nor a scalar in the relation. Consequently, whether a form in relative motion is accelerating or in uniform motion in relation to other forms in relative motion, the relative motion and absolute motion of the form is not additive in the relations of spatial difference; stated otherwise: the total velocity of a form in the relational difference of space

is not determined by adding the speed of absolute motion to the velocity of relative motion. Importantly however, the absolute motion of a form will demonstrate vector qualities by its local form pointedly through the relation of the form in relative motion to other forms. That is: the magnitude and the direction of absolute motion become observable in the relations of the relative motion of forms. These vector qualities of absolute motion proposedly observable in relative space relations are reasoned to represent detectable *absolutistic effects* that allow for verification or falsification of the theorization of a whole-reality simultaneously in relative and absolute motion. They can also be understood to rationally provide the “extra-relativistic facts” (Pooley, 2008, p. 462) required to rebut the *detenser* objection as in principle holds that no spatial or temporal experiential phenomena can fall outside the domain of Einstein’s relativistic physics.

The first absolutistic effect, so referenced, is theorized to be observable via the relative form motion of light, which in Maxwell’s theory of electromagnetism is deemed an electromagnetic wave. Maxwell’s equations leave no provision for light as such to have a relative velocity that may differ according to the frame of reference. In the whole-reasoned motion of form the fixed value of the speed of light (3.00×10^8 m/s) in a vacuum is recognized to ever occur in motion relative to other forms, and in this relation of relative form motion to reflect the magnitude, or velocity, of the absolute motion of forms. This interpretation thus accepts one of special relativity’s foundational postulates, i.e. that light propagates through empty space with a definite speed c independent of the speed of the source or observer, yet understands this constancy of light in relative motion and the speed limit represented thereby to be a function of absolute form motion. *Moreover, the magnitude of the speed limit of forms in relative motion is determined by the magnitude of the absolute motion of the space-form-time universe as an actualizing non-local whole, and it is by the definite and delimited magnitude of absolute motion that motion constancy is conferred on the speed of light in a vacuum across all reference frames in relative motion.* The absolutistic effect of the constancy of the speed of light is thence reasoned to give rise to relativistic effects in the relative motion of forms – like time dilation and length contraction. It is however beyond the scope of the essay to expound these.

The second absolutistic effect – which constitutes the content of the proposed cosmological dynamic – is hypothesized to be empirically observable firstly in the accelerated expansion of the universe, and secondly in the unexpectedly high rotational velocities of galaxies in a cluster, and

also of stars inside galaxies. It is in the attempt to explain the former finding, as earlier discussed, that scientists have introduced the concept of dark energy into their cosmological models. Now in the subscribed whole-reasoning of form motion it is determined that the supposed cosmological action of dark energy as a repulsive force unwittingly falls under the same category of reasoning error as the supposed outward action of a ‘centrifugal force’ or ‘center-fleeing force’ pulling on an object in circular motion. This determination runs as a rational outcome of the theorization whereby the absolute motion of the universe as a non-local whole is given a *substantialist* interpretation and therein reasoned to have a round-going geometric shape by the following logic: the logic emmanal nature of whole-universe motion rationally sets the spatio-temporal requirement of the universe beginning and universe ending to be different local identities and also the same non-local identity. The selected geometry of a round-going shape satisfies this logical condition by allowing the distinctive identities of universe beginning and ending to be recognized as different points on the specified circumference, and yet also come together in the same point on the circumference and so be recognized as a shared identity.⁸

In light of the afore-reasoned geometry of absolute motion the physics of objects in circular motion, i.e. *circular kinematics*, hence becomes applicable to the modelling of whole-universe motion. To demonstrate by way of analogy: imagine a hand swinging a ball on the end of a string at a constant velocity in a circle and generating a certain angular momentum. In accordance with Newton’s first law of motion, the hand (via the string) is exerting a force on the ball – continuously pulling the ball out of its natural straight-line path (its inertial path) towards the center of the circle, so making the ball move in a circle. Importantly, the only force on the rotating ball (ignoring an obvious force like gravity) is the one exerted *inwardly* on it by the hand; whereby, accordant with Newton’s third law of motion, the ball exerts an equal and opposite force on the hand. Recognize that there is no force *outwardly* exerted on the ball, no centrifugal force. This is evidenced by the fact that when the hand releases the ball (and no longer exerts an inward force) it does not fly outward as would be expected from an outward acting force; instead the ball simply flies off tangentially in the direction of its velocity at the moment of release. As such it is understood that there is no centrifugal force, only the tendency of the ball, loaded with angular momentum, to

⁸ For modelling purposes the dynamic of *reflection symmetry* can be considered in order to establish a logical preference for a closing circular shape as opposed to any other closed shape.

continue on its inertial path in a state of uniform motion, unless the hand again pulls inwards. The latter scenario bears out the principle of Newton's *law of inertia*.

Thus the following cosmological dynamic, or absolutistic effect, is identified for the circular kinematics of whole-universe motion. Let us for demonstration purposes assume an object in absolute motion traces a round-going or rotational spatio-temporal path, one with a hypothetical constancy of radius and velocity around an imaginary fixed axis or axis-line.⁹ By its rotational absolute motion the object will acquire the physical properties or propensities appropriate to circular kinematics, which include, as for the rotating ball, the property of angular momentum. At the same time the principle of inertia will be applicable, whereby the object will demonstrate the propensity to continue in uniform motion on its inertial straight-line path – an object propensity here referred to as *tangential inertia*. These circular kinematics of the object's absolute motion will translate into the dimension of the object's relative motion as the object being freely released, 'thrown' as it were, in the direction of the universe's absolute motion at the moment of release, a direction ever tangential to its rotational motion at the point of release. During the release of the object in its tangential inertia, the angular momentum generated by the object's rotational absolute motion, denoted *absolute momentum*, will come to bear on the relative motion of the object in its relative space relations to other objects; and seeing as the object by itself – a *non-thing-in-itself* by its logic emmanal nature – does not exist in vectorial relation to its absolute motion, the specified momentum will be conferred onto the object in no absolute or fixed direction in relative space, but proposedly in the direction of the object's actual relative motion (i.e. the relative direction of its current velocity) in spatial and temporal relation to other objects in difference.

It further follows for the circular kinematics of whole-universe motion that absolute form motion is accounted a *non-inertial absolute frame of reference* – since it constantly changes direction without any apparent force acting on it. Such is understood in the meaning of a *whirligig universe*.¹⁰

Regarding the magnitude of the conferred absolute momentum and its correlating absolutistic effect, consider the angular momentum formula for an object rotating about a fixed axis:

⁹ The round-going shape is possible in various forms; for example: in its simplest form it may be a round-going circle with constant radius; or it may be a *forward* moving helical form with constant radius, or a forward moving spiral form with increasing and/or decreasing form. The model will have to be put into dialectic with the object in order to determine the perfectly logical reflection version.

¹⁰ The naming is inspired by Shakespeare's phrase 'the whirligig of time' in *Twelfth Night* Act 5, Scene 1.

$L = I \omega$, where L is the angular momentum, I is the moment of inertia, and ω is the angular velocity; which in turn can be written as: $L = m r^2 \omega$, where m is the mass; r is the radius (distance from rotation axis). The absolute momentum of an object can further be expressed as *absolute rotational kinetic energy* by the formula: $KE = \frac{1}{2} I \omega^2$. Hence, the larger the mass, radius and angular velocity of an object in its rotational absolute motion about a fixed axis or axis-line, the larger the angular momentum conferred on the object in relative motion to other objects in difference. Thus understood, and assuming that *rotational absolute form motion* remains constant in the magnitude of both its angular velocity and radius¹¹, it becomes apparent that the magnitude of the conferred absolute momentum will in the main be determined by the mass of the object in relative motion. So it comes to reason: for an object with relatively small mass (like a particle) in comparison to an object with large mass (like a planet), the absolute momentum of its tangential inertia will be relatively small. As the object combines with other objects to form larger and larger composite objects (as occurs in gravitational matter clumping), so the new object will come to relationally carry in its absolute motion increased absolute momentum – which is ever released in the direction of its current velocity of relative motion. The latter cosmological dynamic will ordinarily become significant as an absolutistic effect once the object mass is sufficiently large in difference relations and the counter-acting tangential forces, like gravity (the analogical pulling-hand), are sufficiently weak in comparison. In the cosmological scenario where large astronomical distances have opened up between large astronomical objects like galaxies, it may hence occur that the increased absolute momentum of the astronomical object, in combination with the remaining linear momentum carried over from that object's previous relative motion, begins to sufficiently overcome the strength of gravity's inward pull and so cause the relative motion of the object to increase in velocity away from the gravitational pull (in the direction of its observed relative motion). This proposition of a cosmological dynamic by which absolute momentum is generated through the tangential inertia of an astronomical object in rotational absolute motion thus gives explanation for the earlier discussed finding of accelerated universe expansion. It is reasoned that in such cases as the earlier noted Type Ia supernovae the absolute momentum conferred on their relative motion has come to significantly exceed the counter-acting tangential force of gravity, and so is causing

¹¹ It is accepted for the relation of the absolute motion dimension to the relative motion dimension that all forms in motion are to be considered *equidistant* from the imagined axis or axis-line of rotational absolute form motion. Hence the quantity of radius in the angular momentum formula for rotational absolute motion here represents a constant shared by every form. This allows the relation of linear velocity to angular velocity to be expressed as $v = k\omega$.

these astronomical objects to fly away at an accelerated rate. Most notably for the crisis in modern cosmology: by performing the scientific dialectic of concept and object over a whole form instead of an elemental form of reason, a cosmological principle is produced that pierces the appearance of some additional force acting on the objects in question. Just as there is no outward force – the supposed centrifugal force – acting on a ball swinging in a circle, so there is no repulsive force – the supposed dark energy – pushing astronomical objects outward into expansion. What is to be reflectively saved in the kinematics of our adjudged expanding universe with its negative deceleration parameter (q), is the rationally observed absolutistic effect of massive astronomical objects being released perpetually and powerfully along their inertial paths. For this our cosmological knowledge may explicatively emulate a whirligig universe unto the non-local whole. The same cosmological principle (or dynamic) is effective in concernedly explaining the earlier finding of unexpectedly high rotational velocities for galaxies within clusters and stars within galaxies. Although there may possibly be many astrophysical cases containing actual gravitating objects that today transit undetected before our best scientific competencies of technological and methodological observation (as may include sub-luminous MACHOs)¹² – which can correctly be registered as *baryonic* dark matter – the proposed cosmological principle argues against deriving the gravitational existence of an exotic non-baryonic state of dark matter (like certain WIMPs)¹³ *specifically* from the noted anomalous orbital behaviour of significantly sized astronomical objects.¹⁴ Instead, the aforesaid principle reasons in favour of its own occurrence as the absolutistic effect of a whirligig universe in the next manner. For any astronomical object with large mass that in its relative motion orbits another object or objects with altogether greater mass there are two prime physical propensities at work. The first corresponds to Newton's first law of motion whereby the orbiting object will seek to continue in a straight line unless compelled to change that state by a net force acting on it – *the propensity of inertia*. The second is the propensity of the object to accelerate inward to the attractive center and its prevailing gravitational pull – *the propensity of centripetal or radial acceleration*. The co-occurrence of these two propensities will cause the object to be deflected from its inertial (straight-line) path onto the actual path traced by its orbit

¹² Massive Compact Halo Objects

¹³ Weakly-Interacting-Massive-Particles

¹⁴ The supposed evidence for dark matter includes indirect observational phenomena identified, for example, in gravitational lensing and the cosmic microwave background. The epistemological dialectic of whole-reason has however not yet been elaborated to consider these scientific aspects, and so presently only concerns the anomalous orbital behaviour of large astronomical objects related to the dark matter hypothesis.

about the attractive center. Hereupon the absolute momentum of the object in its rotational absolute motion is reasoned to release onto the object as an additional propensity to accelerate its velocity of relative motion in the direction of its actual path of orbit – *the propensity of non-inertial acceleration*. Hence such a further propensity effected by the proposed cosmological dynamic will perform two vital cosmological functions: Firstly, by passing in the same direction as the object's immediately inward-inclining actual path it will serve to stabilize the actual orbital path followed by the object around the gravitational center – this is expected to prove a key function in the formation process of observed universe structures like protogalaxies, star systems and galaxy clusters. Secondly, by passing from absolute momentum into relative kinetic energy it will constantly accelerate the relative orbital motion of the object – this is understood to provide a key factor in the production of flat rotation curves observed for objects orbiting at velocities that exceed the explanatory power of Newtonian mechanics wanting for more gravitational mass.

Brief mention can be made of two implicated theoretical links to explore: further investigation into the powers and parameters of the imperfectly logical reflections of dark energy and dark matter are expected to yield significant conceptual links and/or measurement correlations; such will however be ontologically specious (as will be models for interactional or interchangeable dark energy and dark matter), since these dark sector components are here reasoned to represent misinterpretations of different astronomical manifestations of the same cosmological dynamic. Secondly implicated –: the cosmological principle, specifically by its production in relative object motion of non-inertial acceleration, is expected to link to the transition acceleration value (a_0) as determined in the astrophysical theory of *Modified Newtonian Dynamics* (MOND). The cosmological principle, moreover, could potentially provide the underlying conceptual basis lacking in MOND for the *ad hoc* introduction of its acceleration parameter, and help clarify why MOND is successful in describing flat rotation curves at the galactic scale but is shown to fail at the cosmological scale (for example see Markevitch et al., 2004; for discussion see Sanders, 2010).

Further to the above demonstration of the discovery directive of dialectic epistemology, a speculative line of whole-reasoning can be sharply noted in conclusion. Regarding the circular kinematics and absolutistic effects as theorized for the whole-universe over its relative and absolute dimensions of motion, consider how an object in its relative motion is understood to exist in no vectorial relation to its absolute motion, and how in consequence the absolute momentum

generated by the object's rotational absolute motion is not conferred onto the object in any absolute or fixed direction in relative space – with the referred momentum proposedly only being conferred in the direction of the object's actual relative motion in spatial and temporal relation to other objects in difference. As such, the rotational or round-going geometric shape of a whirligig universe will expectedly not directly act upon the object to cause any directional change in its relative motion. One can however argue for the rational possibility that the rotational geometric shape of whole-universe motion could under certain differential mass-energy and/or spatio-temporal conditions produce a significant effect on local curvatures of space-time itself, which in turn could create, similar to general relativity or quantum loop gravity, a directional effect in the relative motion of the object. In this manner, moreover, the geometric shape of the whirligig universe could potentially translate into a wide spectrum of observable spatio-temporal-forma patterns of object motion – ranging from minute particle movements (e.g. extraordinary gravitational effects on long-ranging light rays) to massive cosmic formations (e.g. spiral-shaped galaxies).

This order of spatio-temporal-forma patterns, *ex hypothesi*, will have to be derivable in the geometry of their objectal evolutions and/or formations from the proposed influence of *a pervading* rotational absolute motion. The referred influential motion may well extend to, and so be observable in, the growth dynamics of organic objects.

2. References

- Arbey, A., & Mahmoudi, F. (2021). Dark matter and the early universe: a review. *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics*, 119, 103865.
- Arun, K., Gudennavar, S. B., & Sivaram, C. (2017). Dark matter, dark energy, and alternate models: a review. *Advances in Space Research*, 60(1), 166-186.
- Bidin, C. M., Carraro, G., Mendez, R. A., & van Altena, W. F. (2010). No evidence for dark matter disk within 4 kpc from galactic plane. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 724, L122-L126.
- Bidin, C. M., Carraro, G., Mendez, R. A., & Smith, R. (2012). Kinematical and chemical vertical structure of the galactic thick disk. II. A lack of dark matter in the solar neighbourhood. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 751, 30-44.

- Bidin, C. M., Carraro, G., Mendez, R. A., & Moyano, M. (2014). On the local dark matter density. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 573, A91.
- Chadha-Day, F., Ellis, J., & Marsh, D. J. E. (2022). Axion dark matter: what is it and why now? *Science Advances*, 8(8), eabj3618.
- Dreyer, V.M. (2022). The epistemology and science of justified reason. *Philosophia*, 50, 503-532.
- Hauser, J., & Dröscher, W. (2017). Gravity beyond Einstein? Part I: physics and the trouble with experiments, *Z. Naturforsch*, 72(6)a, 493-525.
- Markevitch, M., Gonzalez, A. H., Clowe, D., Vikhlinin, A., Forman, W., Jones, C., Murray, S., & Tucker, W. (2004). Direct constraints on the dark matter self-interaction cross section from the merging galaxy cluster 1E 0657-56. *Astrophys. J.*, 606, 819-824.
- Nicolson, I. (2007). *Dark side of the universe: dark matter, dark energy, and the fate of the cosmos*. Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Peebles, P. J. E., & Ratra, B. (2003). The cosmological constant and dark energy. *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 75, 559.
- Perlmutter, S., Aldering, G., Goldhaber, G., Knop, R. A., Nugent, P., Castro, P. G., Deustua, S., Fabbro, S., Goobar, A., Groom, D.E., & Hook, I. M. (1999). Measurements of Ω and Λ from 42 high-redshift supernovae. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 517(2), 565.
- Pooley, O. (2008). Space and time. In C. Martin, & P. Stathis (Eds.), *The Routledge companion to philosophy of science* (pp. 452-467). New York: Routledge.
- Popper, K. R. (2002). *The logic of scientific discovery*. London: Routledge.
- Riess, A. G., Filippenko, A. V., Challis, P., Clocchiatti, A., Diercks, A., Garnavich, P. M., Gilliland, R.L., Hogan, C.J., Jha, S., Kirshner, R.P. and Leibundgut, B.R.U.N.O., (1998). Observational evidence from supernovae for an accelerating universe and a cosmological constant. *The Astronomical Journal*, 116(3), 1009.
- Rubin, V. C., & Ford Jr., W. K. (1970). Rotation of the Andromeda nebula from a spectroscopic survey of emission regions. *Astrophys. J.* 159, 379-403.
- Rubin, V.C., Ford Jr., W.K., & Thonnard, N. (1980). Rotational properties of 21 SC galaxies with a large range of luminosities and radii, from NGC 4605 /R = 4kpc/ to UGC 2885 /R =122 kpc/. *Astrophys. J.*, 238, 471-487.
- Sanders, R. H. (2010). *The dark matter problem: a historical perspective*. Cambridge:

Cambridge University Press.

- Sivaram, C. (1994). Mond, dark matter and the cosmological constant. *Astrophys. Space Sci.* 219, 135-141.
- Sivaram, C. (1999). A non-anthropropic origin for a small cosmological constant. *Mod. Phys. Lett. A* 14, 2363-2366.
- Vagnozzi, S., Visinelli, L., Brax, P., Davis, A-C., & Sakstein, J. (2021). Direct detection of dark energy: the XENON1T excess and future prospects. *Physical Review D*, 104, 063023.
- Wang, B., Abdalla, E., Atrio-Barandela, F., & Pavon, D. (2016). Dark matter and dark energy interactions: theoretical challenges, cosmological implications and observational signatures. *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 79(9), 096901.
- Zwicky, F. (1937). On the masses of nebulae and of clusters of nebulae. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 86, 217.